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LETTER

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Supplementary material for this article is available [online](#)

Abstract

Nitrogen vacancy (NV) color centers in diamond have shown great potential for various applications in quantum technology due to their long coherence times, high sensitivity to magnetic fields and atomic scale resolution. However, one major challenge in utilizing near surface NV centers is the decoherence caused by spins and charges fluctuating on the surface, which affects the spin properties of the sensors. To reduce the induced noise, various oxygen surface treatments such as low power oxygen plasma treatment and annealing under oxygen atmosphere have been explored to terminate the diamond surface and reduce its impact on NV coherence. We showed that the NV center's coherence time can be enhanced up to a factor of 3 over a large spectral range of noise. Double electron–electron resonance measurements revealed an extra source of decoherence, scaling similarly as the P1 spin bath. The improvement in coherence times is accompanied with an increase in measured ketone/ether content and reduction of sp^2 signal in x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy measurements. Finally we compared the performance of different NV ensembles and surface treatments for sensing external proton spins. The oxygen annealing is an effective procedure of enhancing the spin coherence times and reducing broad band spin noise experienced by shallow implanted ensemble NV centers in diamond.

1. Introduction

The negatively charged nitrogen vacancy center (NV^-) can be profitably deployed as a nanoscale sensor. The sensitivity of the defect's electronic spin to magnetic fields, electric fields, strain and temperature [1], allows the NV center to be used in various metrological fields, such as nanoscale nuclear magnetic resonance [2, 3] and thermometry [4]. To achieve single spin resolution, the NV sensors must be located only a few nanometers below the diamond surface [5–7]. However, the diamond surface plays host to various defects which limit the coherence times of shallow NV sensors [8, 9]. The origin of these surface defects and their influence, which limits reliable and reproducible measurement protocols with near-surface NV centers, are not yet fully understood. However, the creation of carbonyl surface species has been connected to oxygen surface treatments, which are a potential source of electromagnetic noise [10].

This work systematically changes the diamond surface composition by using different oxygen termination techniques to minimize the impact of surface noise on implanted NV ensembles. We study different NV-rich regions on a single substrate that were created using nitrogen ion implantation with implantation doses of $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $3 \times 10^{12} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and kinetic energies of 1.5 keV, 2.5 keV and 5 keV. The electron spin coherence times and relaxation times were measured after

each surface treatment. Double electron–electron resonance (DEER) spectra taken after each sample termination step allowed the NV center’s paramagnetic environment to be probed [11]. Surface noise spectra measured using the Carr–Purcell–Meiboom–Gill (CPMG) sequence show the noise level experienced by the NV ensembles in the broad MHz regime. Throughout the diamond surface treatments, x-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) revealed the dynamics of oxygen related functional groups and sp^2 defects present at the diamond–air interface. This study contributes to a better understanding of the diamond surface and its influence on shallow NV spin properties resulting from different oxygen termination methods. As a result, color center creation parameters which optimize external spin sensitivity, such as surface termination and depth, can be determined for NV ensemble based applications. This is necessary for, for example, non-invasive nuclear magnetic resonance of external cells.

2. Sample preparation and methods

The sample used in this work is a $1 \times 1 \times 0.5 \text{ mm}^3$ type IIa electronic-grade single crystal diamond substrate from Element Six with (100) face orientation. Before overgrowth and ion implantation, the diamond was cleaned in a boiling 1 : 1 : 1 triacid mixture consisting of sulfuric acid, nitric acid and perchloric acid at 200°C for 30 min.

The sample was overgrown in a home built microwave assisted chemical vapor deposition reactor with a 150 nm thick ultra-pure ^{12}C layer to minimize ^{13}C nuclear spins from influencing the spin properties of the subsequently implanted NV centers [12]. The sample was then implanted with $^{15}\text{N}^+$ ions at 3 implantation energies (1.5 keV, 2.5 keV and 5 keV) and 3 nitrogen doses ($1 \times 10^{12} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$, $3 \times 10^{12} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$), resulting in 9 separate implantation regions. Finally, the sample was annealed in vacuum at 1000°C for 3 h to form charge stable NV centers within the implanted regions [13].

After NV creation, the sample was treated with (1) triacid boiling, (2) inductively-coupled soft etch oxygen plasma and (3) annealed under a flowing oxygen atmosphere at 480°C for 4 h as illustrated in figure 1(a) (see also supplementary information). The spin properties of the same NV ensembles at each implantation spot and the diamond surface’s chemical composition are probed after each termination step using a confocal microscope and a commercial XPS machine.

3. Results

We first measured the spin coherence time of the implanted NV ensembles after each surface treatment. The measured signal was fitted with a stretched exponential of form $C_0 \exp\{-(\tau/T_2)^\beta\}$ to extract the spin relaxation time T_2 [14]. Figure 1(b) shows measured Hahn echo T_2 coherence times of the NV ensembles together with their depth, which is determined by sensing the proton spins within the immersion oil [15]. As the NV ensembles in this study are intrinsically characterized by a depth distribution from ion implantation, the measured values from here on represent spatial averaged values.

The oxygen plasma treatment (2) results in enhanced T_2 times compared to the triacid treatment (1) across all NV ensembles. It is known that oxygen plasma can etch away the diamond surface depending on the parameters used [16, 17]. The evident increase in T_2 after the treatment indicates that the surface was altered by the plasma. Further, we applied O_2 annealing of the sample at 480°C (3) after the soft etch treatment and found even further improved spin echo times, as also shown by Sangtawesin *et al* [8]. The high temperature of the oxygen annealing process selectively etches sp^2 carbon whereas the soft etch plasma is aggressive enough to remove sp^3 carbon and sp^2 hybridized carbon [18]. Note that the enhancement of T_2 due to the surface treatments is clearly visible for the shallowest NV centers, while this effect is getting weaker starting at a depth of $d \approx 10 \text{ nm}$. Similar results were measured for the spin-lattice relaxation times shown in figure 1(c) for all NV ensembles. O_2 plasma treatment (2) after triacid boiling (1) significantly increases the T_1 relaxation time. Further treatment of the diamond using oxygen annealing (3) improves the longitudinal relaxation times only slightly.

Additionally, the NV charge state stability showed similar scaling with the different oxygen termination techniques than the NV spin coherence times (see supplementary information).

To investigate the effects of previous sample treatments, a final secondary O_2 plasma treatment (4) was applied. As shown in figures 1(b) and (c), this last plasma treatment led to a slight reduction in both T_2 and T_1 times, showing the reversibility of the termination processes. This reduction could be attributed to a combination of factors, including changes in the chemical surface composition, increased surface damage from the plasma, and a reduced distance between the NV centers and the diamond surface.

For NV centers created from ion implantation, the concentration of substitutional nitrogen (P1) centers tends to be very high because the lack of vacancies after implantation limits the NV creation yield [19–21]. Therefore, in addition to the diamond surface contribution, two important sources of decoherence for

shallow implanted NV centers are P1 centers and vacancy related defects due to the induced implantation damage. To find possible reasons for the coherence time enhancement shown in figure 1, the paramagnetic spin environment around the NV centers was probed by Hahn echo based DEER measurements.

Bauch *et al* [14] showed that, for NV centers in bulk diamond, the coherence time is limited to a large extent by the nitrogen content of the diamond. Here we compare the correlation of Hahn echo coherence times and measured paramagnetic spin densities around shallow NV centers, for all performed surface treatments (see figure 1(a)), with the same correlation from Bauch *et al* [14]. To this end the total nitrogen content $[\text{N}]$ in Bauch *et al* [14] is converted into a P1 content $[\text{P1}] = 0.45..0.87 \cdot [\text{N}]$ according to results reported by Osterkamp *et al* [22] and Edmonds *et al* [23], and marked as dark gray band in figure 2. This can then be compared with our coherence data taken as a function of the total paramagnetic spin concentration, $[\text{s}]$, which includes P1 centers, implantation damage induced $g \sim 2$ spins, and contributions from the surface.

The model proposed by Bauch *et al* [14] assumes an inverse scaling of the coherence time with the nitrogen concentration $[\text{N}]$ and other sources of decoherence T_2^{other} in the regime of negligibly small nitrogen concentrations:

$$\frac{1}{T_2([\text{N}])} = B_{\text{NV-N}} \times [\text{N}] + \frac{1}{T_2^{\text{other}}}, \quad (1)$$

with the nitrogen-dominated NV decoherence rate per unit density $B_{\text{NV-N}}$.

Our measured coherence times scaling with the total paramagnetic spin concentration $[\text{s}]$ (see supplementary information for details) shows similar characteristics compared to the model suggested by Bauch *et al* as shown in figure 2(a). However, all NV ensembles across different surface treatments show an offset towards smaller $B_{\text{NV-N}}$ values (see figure 2(a)) compared to a pure P1 spin bath in bulk diamond. This indicates that, additionally to the detected paramagnetic spin concentration (i.e. P1 and $g \sim 2$), another source of decoherence is present which shows similar scaling behavior.

The triacid treated (1) diamond surface shows different scaling behavior which can be explained by the large influence of the $[g \sim 2]$ signal (see figure 2(b)). For subsequent surface treatments, the $[g \sim 2]$

Figure 2. (a) shows the Hahn echo T_2 values as function of the extracted paramagnetic spin concentrations [s] from the measured DEER spectra together with the model fit from Bauch *et al* [14], assuming a (45–87)% fraction of the total nitrogen content within a diamond substrate to be in the P1 configuration (dark gray interval) [22, 23]. (b) and (c) show the paramagnetic spin concentration from (a) divided into its P1 and $g \sim 2$ components, respectively. Model fits according to equation (1) are a guide to the eye.

concentration is significantly reduced up to a factor of ≈ 5 . A possible reason could be that the O_2 plasma takes away the damaged surface layer from implantation. This is supported by the change in $g \sim 2$ concentration in figure 2(b) that is more pronounced for shallow NV centers. Further, after the first O_2 plasma etch, the influence of $g \sim 2$ spins shows little variations. It must be mentioned that in our model the $g \sim 2$ signal is attributed to spin 1/2 systems. However, higher spin systems might also exist within the $g \sim 2$ region. Therefore, a systematical error in underestimating the $g \sim 2$ concentration is possible.

The NV ensemble's coherence time at the limit of small P1 concentration, T_2^{other} , is more strongly limited for shallower sensors, as shown with black model curves in figure 2(c). Values of $T_2^{\text{other}} = (10 \pm 2) \mu\text{s}$, $(15 \pm 3) \mu\text{s}$ and $(107 \pm 57) \mu\text{s}$ (1.5 keV, 2.5 keV and 5 keV, respectively) indicate that surface associated spins are a major source of decoherence.

All surface treatments result in a higher [$g \sim 2$] concentration than [P1] (compare figures 2(b) and (c)). A similar effect was also observed by Tetienne *et al* [24] for NV ensembles implanted with energies up to

14 keV. They found a reduction of the $g \sim 2$ peak after annealing at 1200°C . This indicates that, together with our observation of a reduced $g \sim 2$ peak after O_2 plasma treatment (2), the origin of this signal lies in the ion implantation damage.

To locate explicit sources of magnetic noise in the vicinity of the NV centers, including the diamond surface, CPMG based noise spectroscopy was performed. The dynamically decoupled contrast signal was fitted with a stretched exponential of form $C_0 \exp\{-(\tau/T_2^{\text{CPMG}})^\beta\}$ to extract the decay rates $1/T_2^{\text{CPMG}}$ for a specific pulse spacing τ . Figure 3(a) shows measured decay rate curves for the NV ensembles implanted with a dose of $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for all implantation energies.

In general, all noise spectra exhibit a monotonic smooth decrease of decoherence rate towards higher noise frequencies. Spectra with the lowest noise levels seem to asymptotically approach a constant decoherence rate for high frequencies. This asymptotic rate may be set by the longitudinal spin relaxation time T_1 . It can be seen that the total amount of decoherence experienced by the NV ensembles reduces with increasing distance from the diamond surface. Furthermore, the influence of the surface treatments is reduced with increasing depth: NV ensembles implanted with 1.5 keV and 2.5 keV show a significant reduction of the decay rate spectrum after the initial oxygen plasma process (2) while the deepest NV ensembles show small changes across surface treatments. This shows that despite the different surface terminations, spins and charge traps at the diamond surface are a major source of noise for shallow NV centers up to a depth of $d \approx 16 \text{ nm}$.

The triacid treatment (1) results in the highest decay rates across the probed frequency range between 10 kHz–10 MHz. The O_2 plasma treatment (2) reduces the magnetic noise experienced by the NV centers which fits well to the previous improvement of the T_2 values. The least amount of broadband magnetic noise influencing the NV ensembles was measured after O_2 annealing (3). This shows that the oxygen annealing process is efficient in reducing surface noise and therefore enhancing the coherence times of shallow NV centers. The secondary O_2 plasma treatment (4) lifts the noise spectrum up, effectively creating new impurities at the diamond surface and bringing the NV centers closer to it.

It should be noted that simulation results by Freire–Moschovitis *et al* [25] suggest that P1-related noise occurs around 10 kHz–100 kHz, while implantation-related vacancy noise lies in the 100 MHz range. Due to limitations in coherence times and technical constraints, exploration of this broader frequency range was not possible. However, the results presented here show that broad-band noise sources near the diamond surface are influenced by oxygen surface termination.

For higher implantation doses of $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ in figure 3(b), the depth separation of the noise spectra is reduced. The high doses leading to dense NV ensembles result in stronger NV–NV dipolar coupling which lifts the noise spectra to approximately the same level as for the $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ spots implanted with 1.5 keV. This shows that the upper limit in figure 3(a)–(b) is governed by the influence of the diamond surface spins and, for higher implantation doses, the strong dipolar interactions between NV centers.

All NV ensembles show interaction with proton spins in the immersion oil. This results in a loss of coherence at 2.4 MHz which is the Larmor frequency of proton spins at an external magnetic field of around 560 G. We have estimated the photon-shot-noise-limited signal-to-noise-ratio (SNR) per unit measurement time in a proton sensing experiment taking into account the NV density, the related sensing sequence setting and signal visibility (see supporting information). The calculated proton SNR in figure 3(c) suggests that, among our tested settings, a depth of around 7 nm is beneficial for surface spin sensing using ensemble NV centers. A higher density of NV centers up to maximum tested implantation dose of $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ increases the proton SNR. At doses as high as $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and higher (≈ 10 nm distance between NV centers), the NV coherence time starts suffering from NV–NV dipole interaction.

The oxygen annealing (3) results in the highest proton SNR across all implantation spots and surface treatments, thus effectively reducing the measurement time in related sensing applications. Therefore, the annealing under oxygen flow is beneficial for external spin sensing at the diamond surface. Summarizing, we find that the implantation setting 2.5 keV and $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ combined with treatment (3) yields the highest SNR among the tested configurations. For example, it is 8.4 times higher than for 1.5 keV and $1 \times 10^{12} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ and a triacid treated surface (1).

Chemical analysis of the terminated diamond surface using electron spectroscopy was done on equivalent (100) diamond substrates which were prepared with the same processes as the implanted NV sample. The survey spectra of the different oxygen treatments presented in figure 4(a) show a higher O 1s content for the O₂ soft etch plasma process (2) and the O₂ annealing (3) compared to the triacid treatment (1). A measured amount of 8 at% oxygen content was estimated to correspond to approx. 1 monolayer of oxygen on the diamond surface [26]. This shows that the oxygen soft etch plasma as well as the oxygen annealing are more effective in terminating the diamond surface with oxygen related groups compared to triacid treatment.

C 1s detail spectra in figure 4(b) show different oxygen related functional groups bound to the diamond surface. The majority of the signal in the C 1s detail spectrum originates from sp³ carbon at 284.6 eV. Peak deconvolution results in two peak components towards higher binding energy side with a chemical shift of +1.1 eV and +2.5 eV which were assigned to oxygen single and double bonded to carbon, respectively [8, 27]. The peak component at lower binding energy with respect to sp³ at –1 eV is the contribution of sp² carbon and surface defects.

The oxidation by the triacid treatment itself creates a certain amount of sp² hybridized carbon at the diamond surface [26]. The O₂ soft etch plasma treatments leads to higher ketone (C=O) or ether (O–C–O) bonds while at the same time creating significantly more sp² or surface defects signal at the lower binding energy side. The subsequent O₂ annealing results in approximately the same amount of ketone, ether and alcohol (C–OH) related chemical groups covalently bound to carbon atoms. However, the amount of detectable sp² or surface defect signal was significantly reduced. This is expected because the annealing of diamond at temperatures around 450 °C is known to selectively etch sp² carbon [18, 28].

The increase in measured T_2 after O₂ soft etch plasma treatment might originate from a higher oxygen coverage of the diamond as shown in figure 4(a) coming from the increase in ether or ketone groups shown in figure 4(b). Caution is required because the chemical shifts of ether and ketone groups overlap within the C 1s binding energy region, complicating interpretation without additional measurement techniques like near-edge x-ray absorption fine structure spectroscopy. Especially, the ketone bonding is known to be produced by diamond oxygen termination techniques and create low-lying unoccupied electronic states and therefore could well be the source of electromagnetic noise [10, 26]. Further increase in T_2 and reduction of the broad band magnetic noise after O₂ annealing shows that low sp² carbon content is also important [9]. Therefore, the combination of high oxygen coverage, with potentially low ketone content, and low sp² or surface defect signal is crucial for long coherence times of shallow NV centers.

It is important to note that repeated oxygen treatments may lead to hysteresis effects such as introducing sp² components already after triacid treatment. The XPS results in figure 4(b) show an increase in sp² signal after oxygen plasma treatment. However, the observed improvement in coherence times suggests that the primary benefit of this process is the removal of a thin damaged surface layer caused by ion implantation,

Figure 4. The survey scans depicted in (a) show slightly increased O 1s content after oxygen plasma treatment and oxygen annealing. The residue F 1s after O₂ soft etch plasma treatment originates from the plasma chamber. (b) shows C 1s detail spectra of all oxygen surface treatments. Apart from the dominant carbon sp³ contribution, peak deconvolution was done using three smaller peaks assigned to carbon singly and doubly bonded to carbon and carbon sp²/surface defects. See supplementary information for fit parameters.

which persists even after triacid treatment. The oxygen annealing process effectively removes sp² carbon. However, findings by Dontschuk *et al* [10] show that oxygen annealing alone provides less oxygen coverage compared to a combined procedure with triacid treatment. Thus, oxygen annealing alone may be slightly less effective than when combined with chemical wet oxidation.

4. Summary and outlook

A ¹²C overgrown type IIa single crystal diamond with (100) face orientation from ElementSix was implanted with nitrogen of kinetic energies up to 5 keV and doses up to $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ to create shallow NV ensembles. Different oxygen diamond surface terminations were achieved via triacid treatment, O₂ soft etch plasma and O₂ annealing under continuous oxygen gas flow. We found that compared to triacid treatment, the oxygen annealing enhanced the T_2 coherence times and T_1 spin relaxation times up to a factor of 2.7 and 2.9 for the shallowest NV color centers, respectively. Measured paramagnetic spin concentrations revealed an additional component limiting the coherence times of shallow NV centers. The scaling behavior of the unknown component shows the same characteristic as nitrogen limited coherence within diamond substrates. The higher concentration of $g \sim 2$ spins measured within the DEER spectrum compared to P1 signal, originate likely from surface associated spins and the damage induced by the implantation process itself. Identification and elimination of the unknown component promises to approach bulk-NV-like coherence time scaling with local nitrogen density. CPMG like noise spectroscopy showed the effectiveness of O₂ annealing which reduced magnetic broad band noise experienced by shallow NV centers in the range between (0.1 – 10) MHz compared to triacid. NV centers created in a depth of ≈ 7 nm using 2.5 keV kinetic energy and $1 \times 10^{13} \text{ }^{15}\text{N}^+ \text{ cm}^{-2}$ implantation dose could be estimated to show optimal surface proton spin sensitivity after diamond oxygen annealing. Chemical analysis of the diamond surface composition using XPS measurements suggested that a high amount of double bonded oxygen functional groups in combination with low sp² carbon and surface defects related signal lead to enhanced coherence times of the NV electron spin after oxygen annealing.

In conclusion, this study demonstrates the effectiveness of oxygen annealing as diamond surface termination procedure for quantum technology applications. Additionally, we show that the spin bath

environment around locally, shallow implanted NV ensembles and the diamond surface is important for external spin sensing capabilities. Hence, the optimization of paramagnetic spin species around shallow NV sensors promises high magnetic field sensitivity with bulk-NV-like properties. Further considerations include the possibility to remove the remaining sp^2 carbon residues from the diamond surface to further enhance the coherence times of shallow NV centers.

Using the presented creation parameters to produce noise isolated NV center ensembles close to the modified diamond surface with tailored coherence times and depths will be crucial for sensing applications in the future.

Data availability statement

The data cannot be made publicly available upon publication because they are not available in a format that is sufficiently accessible or reusable by other researchers. The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable request from the authors.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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References

- [1] Doherty M W, Manson N B, Delaney P, Jelezko F, Wrachtrup J and Hollenberg L C L 2013 The nitrogen-vacancy colour centre in diamond *Phys. Rep.* **528** 1–45
- [2] Glenn D R, Bucher D B, Lee J, Lukin M D, Park H and Walsworth R L 2018 High-resolution magnetic resonance spectroscopy using a solid-state spin sensor *Nature* **555** 351–4
- [3] Staudacher T, Shi F, Pezzagna S, Meijer J, Du J, Meriles C A, Reinhard F and Wrachtrup J 2013 Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy on a (5-nanometer)³ sample volume *Science* **339** 561–3
- [4] Kucsko G, Maurer P C, Yao N Y, Kubo M, Noh H J, Lo P K, Park H and Lukin M D 2013 Nanometre-scale thermometry in a living cell *Nature* **500** 54–58
- [5] Broadway D A, Tetienne J-P, Stacey A, Wood J D A, Simpson D A, Hall L T and Hollenberg L C L 2018 Quantum probe hyperpolarisation of molecular nuclear spins *Nat. Commun.* **9** 1246
- [6] Müller C *et al* 2014 Nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy with single spin sensitivity *Nat. Commun.* **5** 4703
- [7] Loretz M, Pezzagna S, Meijer J and Degen C L 2014 Nanoscale nuclear magnetic resonance with a 1.9-nm-deep nitrogen-vacancy sensor *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **104** 033102
- [8] Sangtawesin S *et al* 2019 Origins of diamond surface noise probed by correlating single-spin measurements with surface spectroscopy *Phys. Rev. X* **9** 031052
- [9] Stacey A *et al* 2019 Evidence for primal sp^2 defects at the diamond surface: candidates for electron trapping and noise sources *Adv. Mater. Interfaces* **6** 1801449
- [10] Dontschuk N *et al* 2023 X-ray quantification of oxygen groups on diamond surfaces for quantum applications *Mater. Quantum Technol.* **3** 045901
- [11] de Lange G, van der Sar T, Blok M, Wang Z-H, Dobrovitski V and Hanson R 2012 Controlling the quantum dynamics of a mesoscopic spin bath in diamond *Sci. Rep.* **2** 382
- [12] Balasubramanian G *et al* 2009 Ultralong spin coherence time in isotopically engineered diamond *Nat. Mater.* **8** 383–7
- [13] Yamamoto T *et al* 2013 Extending spin coherence times of diamond qubits by high-temperature annealing *Phys. Rev. B* **88** 075206
- [14] Bauch E *et al* 2020 Decoherence of ensembles of nitrogen-vacancy centers in diamond *Phys. Rev. B* **102** 134210
- [15] Pham L M *et al* 2016 NMR technique for determining the depth of shallow nitrogen-vacancy centers in diamond *Phys. Rev. B* **93** 045425

- [16] Kim M, Mamin H J, Sherwood M H, Rettner C T, Frommer J and Rugar D 2014 Effect of oxygen plasma and thermal oxidation on shallow nitrogen-vacancy centers in diamond *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **105** 042406
- [17] de Oliveira F F, Momenzadeh S A, Wang Y, Konuma M, Markham M, Edmonds A M, Denisenko A and Wrachtrup J 2015 Effect of low-damage inductively coupled plasma on shallow nitrogen-vacancy centers in diamond *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **107** 073107
- [18] Osswald S, Yushin G, Mochalin V, Kucheyev S O and Gogotsi Y 2006 Control of sp^2/sp^3 carbon ratio and surface chemistry of nanodiamond powders by selective oxidation in air *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* **128** 11635–42
- [19] Gaebel T *et al* 2006 Room-temperature coherent coupling of single spins in diamond *Nat. Phys.* **2** 408–13
- [20] Rabeau J R, Reichart P, Tamanyan G, Jamieson D N, Praver S, Jelezko F, Gaebel T, Popa I, Domhan M and Wrachtrup J 2006 Implantation of labelled single nitrogen vacancy centers in diamond using ^{15}N *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **88** 023113
- [21] Naydenov B, Richter V, Beck J, Steiner M, Neumann P, Balasubramanian G, Achard J, Jelezko F, Wrachtrup J and Kalish R 2010 Enhanced generation of single optically active spins in diamond by ion implantation *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **96** 163108
- [22] Osterkamp C, Balasubramanian P, Wolff G, Teraji T, Nesladek M and Jelezko F 2020 Benchmark for synthesized diamond sensors based on isotopically engineered nitrogen-vacancy spin ensembles for magnetometry applications *Adv. Quantum Technol.* **3** 2000074
- [23] Edmonds A M *et al* 2021 Characterisation of CVD diamond with high concentrations of nitrogen for magnetic-field sensing applications *Mater. Quantum Technol.* **1** 025001
- [24] Tetienne J-P *et al* 2018 Spin properties of dense near-surface ensembles of nitrogen-vacancy centers in diamond *Phys. Rev. B* **97** 085402
- [25] Freire-Moschovitis F A, Rizzato R, Pershin A, Schepp M R, Allert R D, Todenhagen L M, Brandt M S, Gali A and Bucher D B 2023 The role of electrolytes in the relaxation of near-surface spin defects in diamond *ACS Nano* **17** 10474–85
- [26] Alba G, Villar M P, Alcántara R, Navas J and Araujo D 2020 Surface states of (100) O-terminated diamond: towards other $1 \times 1:O$ reconstruction models *Nanomaterials* **10** 1193
- [27] Wang X, Ruslinda A R, Ishiyama Y, Ishii Y and Kawarada H 2011 Higher coverage of carboxylic acid groups on oxidized single crystal diamond (001) *Diam. Relat. Mater.* **20** 1319–24
- [28] Fu K-M C, Santori C, Barclay P E and Beausoleil R G 2010 Conversion of neutral nitrogen-vacancy centers to negatively charged nitrogen-vacancy centers through selective oxidation *Appl. Phys. Lett.* **96** 121907